

tation. The observation of the lowering of C=O stretching frequency caused by complexation shows that it is in the order, $\text{Hg}^{II} > \text{Zn}^{II} > \text{Cd}^{II}$. This is the same as the order found for the values of thermodynamic stability constants. Therefore, there exists a clear correlation between the lowering of C=O stretching frequency and the stability of the complexes. This can be explained on the basis of the strength of M—O bond. As the M—O bond becomes stronger the C=O bond lengthens and weakens. Hence, the C=O stretching frequency is lowered more. Similar reasoning has been used by Fujita *et al.*¹⁰ to explain bonding in metal oxalate complexes. Bellamy and Branch¹¹ have given a remarkable correlation between C=O stretching frequency and the stability constants for some complexes of salicylaldehyde with metal ions. Therefore, the correlation found in the present case also agrees with the earlier investigation.

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A New Method for the Preparation of Strontium Titanate and Strontium Hypovanadate

M. R. BALASUBRAMANIAN

Department of Chemistry, Government College of Technology, Coimbatore-641 013

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STRONTIUM titanate has been a prized chemical by virtue of its dielectric¹, photoelectric² and surface properties³. The compound crystallises with the cubic perovskite structure⁴ as shown in Fig. 1. Till now only two techniques (and a few variants therein) have been employed for its synthesis, one of them is a solid state reaction⁵ between SrCO_3 and TiO_2 at 1100° , and the other is a coprecipitation⁶ of strontium titanate oxalate followed by calcination at 850° . As ternary oxides, such as copper chromite, have been prepared by complex

formation, the present author found it interesting to apply this method to the preparation of strontium titanate. The most easily accessible and versatile complexing agent, EDTA, was used.

Fig. 1a. Perovskite crystal structure (with ion A at the body centre).

Fig. 1b. Perovskite crystal structure (with ion B at the body centre).

SrVO_3 is also a cubic perovskite containing vanadium in the B sites. It has been prepared earlier⁷ by solid state reaction between SrCO_3 and V_2O_5 in a current of H_2 . It was also proposed to prepare SrVO_3 by this complexing method.

All the chemicals used in the preparation were A.R. or of equivalent grade. For the preparation of Sr-EDTA complex, 7.35 g SrCO_3 and 14.6 g EDTA (free acid) were mixed and the mixture was taken into a well-stoppered polythene bottle. 150 ml water was added and the slurry gently shaken, taking care to allow the evolved CO_2 to escape smoothly. When the dissolution was complete, the pH of the solution was adjusted to 9 by the addition of NH_4OH . For the preparation of Ti-EDTA complex, 4 g TiO_2 was dissolved in about 40 ml HF and the mixture was cooled in ice. The supernatant liquid was tested for complete precipitation. The precipitate was filtered and washed free of F^- and NH_4^+ . It was then dissolved in minimum amount of dilute HCl and 14.6 g EDTA and 150 ml water were added to the solution. Preparation of the above two metal-EDTA complexes was carried out following the general procedure for the preparation of such complexes⁸.

The solutions of the above two metal-EDTA complexes were evaporated separately on a water bath to a small volume. The crystals were deposited from the solution by adding acetone. The supernatant liquid was drained and the crystals were mixed. The mixture was again dissolved in a minimum amount of water and allowed to evaporate. Cooling in ice or addition of acetone brought about crystallisation of the complexes in admixture. Before draining the supernatant liquid it was tested and the absence of both the metal ions in it was ensured. The crystals were dried and calcined in a mullite

boat. Initially the temperature was slowly raised to 300° till the evolution of gases ceased. Then the temperature was raised to 600° in 12 h and to 700° in another 12 h. The sample was kept at 700° for another 12 h with cooling and grinding at the end of every 4 h.

A similar procedure was adopted for the preparation of the EDTA complexes of Sr and V, except that the two metal complexes were prepared in the same solution in view of the high solubility of the vanadium compound.

Usual chemical analysis⁹ was carried out on the prepared samples. The products were also characterised by X-ray diffraction (for powdered samples in a Dron⁻¹ unit with CuK radiation), thermal analysis (in a MOM derivatograph), infrared spectroscopy (in a Perkin-Elmer spectrophotometer using KBr pellet), esr spectroscopy (in a Varian-112 spectrometer and a TCNE marker), optical spectroscopy (for SrTiO₃ only in a Cary-17 D spectrophotometer) and electrical conductivity (for SrTiO₃ only using a two-probe method and sintered pellets). Due to the metallic conduction of SrVO₃, its conductivity could not be measured in the available set-up.

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the SrTiO₃ sample could be indexed to a cubic perovskite lattice with a lattice parameter of 3.9 Å in close agreement with the value quoted in literature¹⁰. No other phase was discernible in the pattern. The endothermic peak corresponding to the melting point of TiO₂ was absent in the derivatogram. This confirms the completion of the reaction. The infrared spectrum of the sample showed a band around 500 cm⁻¹ which has been ascribed to the presence of TiO₆ octahedra¹¹. ESR spectrum at 113 K contained a six-line signal consistent with the hyperfine splitting of the Ti isotopes with nuclear spin 5/2. Occurrence of this sharp signal points to the presence in traces of Ti²⁺ ion. This is further confirmed by the yellow colour of the samples and the broad band at 340 nm in the optical spectrum. Electrical conductivity of the sample measured at room temperature was 2 × 10⁻⁹ Ω⁻¹ cm⁻¹, and the energy of activation in the temperature range of 25-600° was 1.04 eV. This low level of conductivity can only be due to the presence of Ti²⁺ ions in traces.

The X-ray diffraction pattern of the SrVO₃ sample could be indexed to a cubic perovskite sample lattice with a lattice parameter of 3.84 Å in agreement with the value reported in literature¹². The endothermic peak due to the melting of V₂O₅ was absent in the derivatogram of the sample indicating clearly the completion of the reaction. The same inference could be drawn from the absence of the band due to the V=O bond in the infrared spectrum of the sample. ESR spectrum had a signal at a 'g' value of 2.078. The 'g' value larger than the free-spin value denotes the covalent character of the V—O bond in the perovskites. The

broad signal denotes the presence of spin-spin interactions.

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Interaction of Alkali with Zinc Sulphate in Aqueous Media

V. K. SHARMA, N. R. BANERJEE
and
(Late) R. P. MITRA

Department of Chemistry, University of Delhi, Delhi-110 007

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PRECIPITATION of basic salts of varying composition had been reported¹⁻⁷ and the phenomenon attributed variously to adsorption of anions⁸, penetration of the anions⁹ into the outer or inner coordination sphere of the metal ion, or formation of polymeric hydrous oxide with hydroxyl bridges between the metal ions¹⁰. The latter postulate was used to explain the relative non-reactivity of hydrous oxides on aging^{4,11}. Weiser and Milligan¹², however, found that gelatinous precipitates of oxides or hydroxides, containing non-stoichiometric amounts of water, became granular on standing (aging). They also concluded from X-ray diffraction data¹³ that water or the residual electrolyte was not bound to the metal ion but was held by adsorption and capillary forces only. Conductance data of Chatterji and Dhar¹⁴ appeared to support this view.

The present work on Zn²⁺ ion, using equilibrium titration technique⁵, has been carried out in view